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Evaluation of the Behavior of Rockfill Material Using Large-Scale Triaxial Tests

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Abstract

This paper describes the behavior of rockfill materials by use of a series of large scale triaxial compression tests at different confining pressures. In this study, an experimental program was performed on rockfill materials from two different sources located in Guilan province, Iran, including mountain materials from Roudbar region and River material of Sefid-Rud. In order to investigate the effects of grading on the shear strength of rockfill materials, both well graded and poorly graded materials have been considered. As well, particle breakage of materials is discussed. The results indicate that the lower the confining pressure, the more the dilative potential. Furthermore, it can be seen that as the confining pressure increases, the failure occurs in higher axial strains.

Keywords: Rockfill, Large Scale, Triaxial Test, Particle Breakage.

1. Introduction

Rockfill materials are widely used in various geotechnical engineering projects such as construction of rockfill and earth dams. The accurate understanding of rockfill materials as the main materials in large dams is essential. Different studies indicate that the shear strength and deformation characteristics of rockfill materials depend on the variety of factors including grain size distribution, void ratio, moisture content, particle breakage and the applied stress levels. Charles & Watts [1] concluded that dilation and compressibility of materials will decrease due to an increase in stress level. The results of the conducted study by Marsal [2] indicate that the shear strength of rockfill materials is directly related to the dry density, roughness, and breakage strength; where the shear strength is diversely related to sizes of particles and coefficient of uniformity (C_u). In a recent study, Bauer et al. [3] investigate the

influence of pressure and density on the rockfill materials behavior by use of constitutive model. They showed that the behavior of rockfill materials depend on the crack propagation within the particles, abrasions and grain breakage. It is well known that coarse materials suffer particle breakage under high stresses. Although particle breakage of some special materials, such as carbonate sands can happen even due to low confining [4]. With regard to the shear strength, it is noteworthy that in well graded materials, the amount of breakage is less and the angle of friction is higher. On the contrary, the poor or uniform grading of materials leads to lower frictional resistance [5]. The results of the experimental studies by Marachi et al. [6] illustrate a significant decline in the internal friction angle as the grain sizes increase. Moreover, the angularity of grains plays a significant role on the shear strength and deformation of the rockfill materials. The deformation caused by crushing in angular materials is more than rounded materials. On the other hand, angular materials have higher shear strength. Gharavy [7] studied the strength and deformation of materials as a function of the pressure history and magnitude of the pressure. It has been concluded that in drained triaxial test, as the confining pressure increases, the angle of friction decrease. Ghanbari et al. [8] assessed the failure criteria for particle breakage of rockfill materials by conducting direct shear and triaxial tests at different confining pressures. Their results showed that the failure of stiffer rockfill materials has a higher dilatancy comparing to softer materials. Another aspect that is coherent from their study is that for high confining pressures, no dilatancy takes place in samples, whereas in low confining pressures, immediately after the axial deformations of 0.5%, the sample undergoes dilatancy and the volumetric strain increases. As well, it can be seen that the friction angle of rockfill materials in large scale direct shear is 3 to 4 degrees more than triaxial test. According to this, it is necessary to consider a higher safety factor in using the friction angle obtained from direct shear test.

The current study presents an investigation on the behavior of rockfill materials using large scale triaxial tests on three different materials.

2. Materials and Experiments

An experimental study was performed on rockfill materials from two different sources located in Guilan province, Iran, including mountain materials from Roudbar region and River material of Sefid-Rud, which are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 : Location of; a) River material (Sefid-Rud, Guilan, Iran), b) Mountain material (Rudbar, Guilan, Iran)

It is noteworthy that the type of rockfill materials of Rudbar is mostly andesite, where the material from Sefid-Rud is dolomite. Figure 2 presents an image of materials under study. To figure out the influence of improper performance of grading, two well graded and poor graded curves have been employed in triaxial tests. Figure 3 shows grading curves of employed materials.

Figure 2 :Main parts of employed materials; a) River material, b) Mountain material

Figure 3 :Grading curves of rockfill materials

The numbers of 25 consolidated-drained (CD) triaxial tests have been conducted at a wide range of confining pressures (0.05, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5 and 0.7 MPa). All experimental samples have been prepared from the modified standard proctor tests with the dry density corresponding to 95% of MDD and OMC. The sample density was 16.8 kN/m³ and the maximum size of the sample was 25 mm. Samples were prepared in dimensions of 153 mm and 302 mm. Moreover, the deviatoric stress has been applied at a rate of 0.76 mm/min. Figure 4 shows a schematic view of the large scale triaxial apparatus.

Figure 4 :The Schematic view of the triaxial compression test

3. Results of Triaxial Tests

In the current study, large scale triaxial compression tests have been conducted on rockfill materials from three different sources. In order to figure out the influence of improper performance of grading, two well graded and poor graded curves have been employed in triaxial tests for rockfill materials. The following sections present the results of the performed triaxial tests.

3.1. Mountain's materials from Rudbar region

Triaxial compression tests have been conducted at confining pressures of 0.05, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5 and 0.7 MPa on the rockfill materials sample of Rudbar region. As mentioned above, mountain's materials have been tested in both well graded and poor graded. Figures 5 illustrate the deviatoric stress versus axial strain curves. As well, Figures 6 show the volumetric strains against axial strain.

Figure 5 : Deviatoric stress versus axial strain mountain's material; a) Well, b) Poor

Figure 6 : Volumetric versus axial strain mountain's material; a) Well, b) Poor

As it is obvious from Figures 2 and 3, in low confining pressures, the failure of samples occur in small strains, whereas for the high confining pressures, the failure of samples occur in large axial strains. It can be seen that well graded materials have higher shear strength in comparison to poorly graded materials. Also, it is coherent from results is that for poor graded materials no dilatancy will occur in samples. Moreover, increasing the confining pressure leads to a decrease in dilatancy.

3.2. Rockfill materials of Sefid-Rud

The rockfill materials of Sefid-Rud have been tested at confining pressures ranging from 0.05 to 0.7 Mpa. As it can be easily seen, the samples tested in confining pressures of 0.05 and 1 Mpa fail with small axial strains (less that 2%), where the samples under high confining pressures show more strains at failure. Figures 7 show the variation of deviatoric stress versus

axial strain for well and poor grading materials. The volume changes of the samples are illustrated in Figures 8.

Figure 7 : Deviatoric stress versus axial strain River's material; a) Well, b) Poor

Figure 8 : Volumetric versus axial strain River's material; a) Well, b) Poor

As shown, the dilative behavior of samples decreases while the confining pressure increases. Also the amount of volume changes in well graded materials is less than that in the poorly graded materials.

4. Particle Breakage

Comparing the results illustrates that the shear strength of samples increases with increasing dilatancy, which tends to decrease with increasing confining pressure. Lee and Seed (1967) demonstrated that, under high pressure, the shear strength of sand increased while the

dilatancy decreased. They attributed this observation to particle crushing and rearrangement during shearing. Miura and O-hara [9] showed that particle breakage could be significant for low-strength granular materials such as decomposed granite, even under low confining pressure. Various studies have been performed to quantify the breakage of particles during shearing. Marsal [10] developed the breakage index, B_g , as a function of the difference between the percentage retained by weight of each grain size fraction before and after the test. In this study, to quantify the degradation of aggregates during shearing, the particle breakage index, B_g , is defined as the ratio of D_{15} of the samples before the test to the D_{15} of samples after the test. The breakage index of all tested samples are presented in the Figure 9.

Figure 9 :Breakage index of tested samples

As it is obvious from Figure 9, the breakage index in the poorly graded rockfill materials is more than the breakage index of well graded materials. However, as the confining pressure increases, the particle breakage of samples increase.

5.Conclusion

In this paper, an experimental study has been conducted to investigate the behavior of rockfill materials taken from two sources located in North of Iran. A series of large scale triaxial compression tests have been conducted at a wide range of confining pressures (0.05, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5 and 0.7 MPa). Note that in order to investigate the influence of improper grading on the shear strength of rockfill materials, both well graded and poor graded materials have been

tested. It can be concluded that the shear strength of well graded materials is higher than that in poorly graded materials. Moreover, as the confining pressure increases, the difference in the shear strength of two types of grading increases. Another aspect that is coherent from conducted triaxial tests is that during shearing the particles start to break. Comparing the results shows that increasing the confining pressure leads to an increase in particle breakage of samples. As well, the particle breakage causes the dilative tendency to decline.

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